

Notes

A Novel Partial Dechlorination of a Pseudo-octahedral *trans* dichloro acetylacetonone bis (benzoyl-hydrazone) Nickel(II) Complex

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WE have recently described the synthesis¹ of the quadridentate ligand acetylacetonone bis (benzoyl-hydrazone) (I).

Under anhydrous condition, the pseudo octahedral sky blue paramagnetic ($\mu=3.17$ BM), non-electrolytic (in nitromethane) complex (II), *trans* dichloro acetylacetonone bis (benzoyl-hydrazone) nickel(II), can be synthesised while in the presence of a trace of water the ligand undergoes enolisation and an orange-yellow coloured, diamagnetic, square planar non-electrolytic acetylacetonone bis (benzoyl-hydratonato) nickel (II) is obtained (III).

It has been now observed that alternate exposure of the skyblue derivative to moist atmosphere followed by keeping over KOH leads to partial dechlorination (in the form of HCl) of the *trans*

dichloro acetylacetonone bis (benzoyl-hydrazone) nickel(II). After a few days, the colour of the complex changes from sky-blue to greenish-yellow and a steady state results. At this stage the complex corresponds to the loss of one co-ordinated chlorine (in the form of HCl) and gives the following analytical results: [Found C=54.0%; H=4.8%; N=13.15%; Cl=8.16%; Ni=13.61%; Calc: C=53.11%; H=4.4%; N=13.05%; Cl=8.27%; Ni=13.68%]. The loss in weight of the dichloro derivative is 7.5% (over KOH at room temperature) (for one HCl; required: 7.85). The new monochloro derivative is soluble in nitrobenzene and methanol. In nitrobenzene it gives a molar conductance value $\Lambda_M = 1.2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating that the chlorine atom is attached in the inner co-ordination sphere. But in methanol, the molar conductance value is $86 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, giving (1:1) electrolyte value due to solvolysis². A five-co-ordinate monomeric structure is thus suggested (IV).

The mother compound, although six-co-ordinate pseudo-octahedral, has an ill-resolved electronic spectrum with only one band at 25 kK. But the partially dechlorinated complex shows a very rich mull electronic spectrum with bands at 5.8, 7.04, 8.3, 10.5 and 23.5 kK. The bands strongly suggest a five co-ordinated structure (IV)³. Infrared spectrum reveals C=N stretch⁴ at 1590 cm^{-1} and-NH stretch⁵ at $3300-3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Its magnetic moment of 2.2 B. M. is rather low for a high-spin 5-co-ordinate nickel(II). It may be indicative of an equilibrium between a high-spin and low-spin 5-co-ordinate structures⁶.

The most likely explanation is that moisture facilitates partial conversion of the-NH-C=O keto group to the enol form-N=C-OH. The enol (-OH) group then gets hydrogen bonded to one of the two chlorines. KOH assists in extracting and absorbing the HCl, thus converting the compound to a five co-ordinate monochloro acetylacetonone (mono benzoyl-hydratonato) nickel (II). The isolation of this compound exposes a very unusual monoketo mono-enol form (i.e., a monobasic

quadridentate behaviour of the ligand). Thus in the sky-blue (II), greenish-yellow (IV) and orange-yellow compound (III), we have successfully unfolded the neutral, monobasic and dibasic characters of the quadridentate Schiff base (I) respectively.

Experimental

The ligand acetylacetone *bis* (benzoyl-hydrazone) and the complex (II) were prepared according to the procedures of our previous work¹.

Physical measurements

Nickel(II) was estimated as *bis* (dimethylglyoximate) nickel(II). Nitrogen was determined by Duma's method. The chloride was determined as silver chloride, and magnetic moment was obtained from corrected χ_M value, using a Gouy balance with $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a calibrant. Nujol mull spectra were run by R. S. I. C., Madras. C, H, analyses as also the IR spectra were carried out by C. D. R. I., Lucknow.

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A Mixed Anion Salt of Beryllium

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In past few years many mixed ligand complexes of metals have been studied by different physico-chemical methods. Potentiometric evidences are available for the formation of 1:1:1 M(II)AB ternary complexes¹⁻⁸ where A is usually EDTA and B a secondary ligand like glycine, salicylic, succinic, tartaric or maleic acid. Survey of the literature

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however, reveals that ternary complexes without the involvement of EDTA have been studied once⁴. The present paper describes the formation of BeAB system where A is an anion of 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) and B of chromotropic acid (CTA).

DNS⁵ and CTA⁶ figure prominently in the discussion of hydroxy carboxylic acids and hydroxy acids respectively. Each of DNS and CTA provides two possible interaction sites.

Experimental

Beryllium sulphate, potassium nitrate, sodium hydroxide (all AnalaR grade), Reidel's DNS and disodium salt of CTA (E. Merck) were used. Solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A Cambridge bench type pH meter was used for pH measurements.

To know the stoichiometry of the Be-DNS & CTA complex, the proton displacements were evaluated titrating solutions containing Be and the concerned ligands in different ratios employing a standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The titration curves are shown in figure. Curve

Figure. : Potentiometric titration curves of CTA, DNS and of both in the absence and presence of Be employing 0.1 M NaOH.

- Curve 1, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA ;
 Curve 2, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS ;
 Curve 3, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS ;
 Curve 4, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ Be ;
 Curve 5, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ CTA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ DNS + $1.66 \times 10^{-3} M$ Be.